

End-to-End Workflow for 3D Digitization of Biological Specimens Using scAnt and Photogrammetry

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Introduction

3D digitization of biological specimens has become a key tool in fields such as taxonomy, museum curation, and scientific research. However, acquiring high-quality three-dimensional models presents several technical challenges, including limited depth of field, proper specimen illumination, and the need for complex post-processing.

scAnt (<https://github.com/evo-biomech/scAnt>; Plum & Labonte, 2021) is a low-cost (>€200), open-source macro 3D scanner designed to automate the creation of full-color 3D digital models of insects of varying sizes. Examples of models generated with scAnt can be found at <http://bit.ly/ScAnt-3D>, as well as in its public collection on [Sketchfab](#).

All structural components of the scanner can be manufactured using 3D printing and laser cutting. The required files are available for download in .ipt, .iam, .stl, and .svg formats from the project repository.

This document aims to describe a practical workflow for the proper execution of 3D digitization of biological samples. To this end, the following aspects are addressed:

- Image acquisition using scAnt
- Image processing (focus stacking and masking)
- 3D reconstruction using photogrammetry

System Overview

Hardware

The scAnt system consists of:

- A camera (FLIR Blackfly)
- A motorized system with three axes (X, Y, Z)
- A rotating dome where the specimen is placed
- A controlled lighting system

Software

The workflow involves the following software components:

- scAnt (Python-based acquisition software)
- Anaconda (environment management)

- Agisoft Metashape (3D reconstruction)
- GIMP (RGB value extraction for masking)
- Helicon Focus (optional, for improved focus stacking)

Requirements

Hardware Requirements

- A computer with sufficient processing capacity
- High RAM availability (recommended for Metashape)
- Adequate storage space for RAW image datasets

Software Requirements

- Anaconda
- Configured scAnt environment
- Agisoft Metashape
- GIMP
- (Optional) Helicon Focus

Data Acquisition with scAnt

Scanner–Computer Connection

Before operating scAnt, it is essential to correctly connect the system to the computer that will be used for digitization. The scanner includes several cables that must be connected prior to launching the software; see **Figure 1** for a schematic overview:

1. **Power supply:** provides power to the scanner. It is recommended to connect this first.
2. **USB connections:**
 - **USB 1:** connects the computer to the internal memory of scAnt.
 - **USB 2:** connects the computer to the FLIR Blackfly camera.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the cable connections between the computer and scAnt.

scAnt Initialization

Once all connections are established, the software can be launched.

1. Open the Anaconda Prompt (**Fig. 2**).
2. Enter the following commands:
 - a. (base) activate scAnt Loads the scAnt environment.
 - b. (User) cd C:\Users\X\Desktop\X Replace X with the directory where the scAnt Python file is located (**Fig. 3**).
 - c. (User) python scAnt.py Executes the main scAnt script.

Figure 2. Anaconda Prompt icon.

Figure 3. Example of commands used to launch scAnt.

User Interface Overview

After a few seconds (depending on system performance), the graphical interface will open (**Fig. 4**). It is divided into two main tabs:

1. **Scan Parameters:** configuration of acquisition settings (framing, lighting, output location).
2. **Post Processing:** configuration of parallel processes (image stacking, mask generation).

Each tab is further subdivided into sections containing adjustable parameters depending on the scanning requirements.

Figure 4. scAnt graphical interface. The default view is displayed once the programme has started. Boxes in different colours have been included to highlight the various sections that can be modified.

Scan Configuration

Scan Parameters

Camera Settings (Yellow box)

This section controls the parameters that directly affect image acquisition:

- **Select Camera:** Allows selection of the camera used to capture images of the specimen. This parameter should not be modified unless the camera connected to scAnt is changed.
- **Exposure Auto:** Automatically adjusts the exposure time. It can be useful for estimating initial values but must be disabled before starting the scanning process.
- **Exposure Time [μ s]:** Controls the duration for which the camera sensor is exposed to light. Longer exposure times allow more light to reach the sensor,

improving image quality. However, the total scanning time increases proportionally with the exposure time.

- *Note:* Increasing exposure time reduces the need for higher gain, resulting in lower image noise. In general, longer exposure leads to higher image quality and improved overall scan results but significantly increases acquisition time. This represents a trade-off between quality and scanning duration.
- **Gain Auto:** Automatically adjusts the camera gain. Similar to *Exposure Auto*, it can be useful for initial setup but should be disabled before scanning.
- **Gain Level [dB]:** Controls the sensitivity of the camera sensor (analogous to ISO in photography). Higher gain increases image brightness but also introduces digital noise, reducing image quality. It is recommended to keep this value as low as possible.
- **Gamma:** Applies contrast correction, mainly affecting midtones. A slight increase is recommended to enhance contrast between the specimen and the background, which can improve the quality of the masks generated during post-processing.
- **Balance Ratio (Red/Blue):** Adjusts white balance to ensure accurate color reproduction of the specimen.
- **Highlight Exposure:** Highlights overexposed areas in bright red and displays normalized color histograms in the lower-right corner. These histograms shift according to the red/blue balance settings.
- **Start/Stop Live View:** Enables real-time visualization from the camera in the main display. This must be active while adjusting parameters to assess image quality and should be disabled before starting the scan.
- **Capture Image:** Captures a single image using the current settings. The image is saved in the output directory defined in the *Output Settings* section.

Once the function of each adjustable parameter has been reviewed, the recommended configuration workflow can be followed.

Before modifying any settings, *Live View* **must be activated**, allowing real-time visualization of the camera output. Initially, the specimen may not be visible, as the default exposure time is typically too high, resulting in an overexposed image. This will be corrected in the following steps.

With *Live View* enabled, the parameters should be adjusted in the following order:

1. **Adjust [Exposure Time].** This parameter directly influences image quality: longer exposure allows more light to reach the sensor, improving image quality. It is recommended to reduce the exposure time until achieving a well-illuminated image that is slightly underexposed. The optimal value depends on the specific specimen.
 - *Note:* Total scan duration increases proportionally with exposure time. For example, an exposure time between 18,000 and 20,000 μs may result in a total scan time of approximately 3 hours.
2. **Enable Highlight Exposure.** This option displays normalized color histograms in the lower-right corner of the *Live View* and highlights overexposed regions in

- bright red. **Important:** No part of the specimen should appear overexposed. If this occurs, reduce the exposure time or gain level.
3. **Adjust [Gain Level].** Gain controls the sensitivity of the camera sensor and therefore affects image brightness. However, increasing gain also increases noise, reducing image quality. It is recommended to keep this value as low as possible, although the optimal setting may vary depending on the specimen.
 4. **Adjust Gamma.** Gamma applies contrast correction, mainly affecting midtones. A **slight increase** is recommended to improve the visual separation between the specimen and the background, facilitating automatic mask generation during post-processing and improving the final result.
 5. **Adjust White Balance [Balance Ratio Red & Blue].** Finally, adjust the red and blue balance ratios to correct the overall color of the image. The goal is to align the normalized color curves displayed in *Live View* as closely as possible, indicating proper color balance and accurate representation of the specimen.

At this stage, the system should be properly configured for image acquisition.

Output Settings (Red box)

This section defines where the images generated by scAnt during the scanning process will be stored. The configuration is carried out as follows:

1. **Select the output folder.** Click on *Choose Output Folder* to open a window where the destination directory can be selected (**Fig. 5**). In this example, the selected folder is *3D_models_DACER_scAnt*.

Figure 5. Example of the window displayed after clicking *Choose Output Folder*.

2. **Assign a project name.** Once the output folder has been selected, the project name must follow a standardized format:

CatalogNumber_Genus-species_3D

Example: 41036_Carabus-ghiliani_3D

Recommendation: Avoid using spaces or special characters (e.g., accents), as they may cause compatibility issues in some systems.

Once the project name is defined, scAnt will automatically generate a new folder within the selected directory when an image is captured (*Capture Image*) or when the scan is initiated.

The resulting folder structure is as follows:

```
3D_models_DACER_scAnt/  
└── 41036_Carabus-ghiliani_3D/  
    ├── RAW  
    └── stacked
```

- **RAW:** contains all original images captured by the scanner in RAW format.
- **stacked:** contains the processed images generated during post-processing (including stacked images, masks, and contours).

At this stage, the output configuration is complete.

Stepper Control (Green box)

This is the final section within the *Scan Parameters* tab. Here, the movement of the three axes of the scAnt system is configured:

- **X axis:** controls the orientation (tilt) of the specimen via the scanner gimbal, defining the viewing angles
- **Y axis:** controls the rotation of the specimen around its own axis using the rotating dome
- **Z axis:** adjusts the distance between the camera and the specimen, controlling the focus depth

The configuration of these axes determines: 1) The number of viewpoints from which images are captured (defined by the number of steps in the X and Y axes); and 2) The number of images taken per viewpoint (defined by the number of steps in the Z axis).

Before modifying any parameters, all axes must be set to their reference positions using the *Home X/Y/Z Axis* functions. Once initialized, **manual control sliders** will be enabled, allowing independent adjustment of each axis:

1. **X and Y Axes Configuration.** The X (tilt) and Y (rotation) axes define the different perspectives from which the specimen will be imaged. The recommended settings are:
 - Step [X Axis] = **50** (default value)
 - Step [Y Axis] = **40** (default is 80)

This configuration provides a good balance between image quality and total scan time. Reducing these values increases angular resolution but significantly increases the number of viewpoints and, consequently, the total acquisition time.

Once the number of steps is defined, use the manual sliders to: 1) Position the specimen parallel to the ground (X axis); and 2) Orient it facing the camera (Y axis). This positioning is useful for later extracting RGB values required for mask generation in the post-processing stage.

Important: The *Max [X Axis]* and *Max [Y Axis]* values should not be modified. They should only be set equal to the corresponding Min values if scAnt is used exclusively for 2D focus stacking.

2. **Z Axis Configuration (Focus Range).** The Z axis controls the camera position relative to the specimen, defining the focus range and the number of images captured per viewpoint. The goal is to define a **focus range** (Min–Max) that fully encompasses the specimen, with a small margin on both ends to ensure complete coverage.

Recommended workflow:

1. **Set the minimum focus limit.** Move the camera away until the front-most part of the specimen is in focus. Capture an image to confirm correct focus. Then, assign a slightly larger Min value (e.g., if focus is achieved at -25,000, set Min to -26,000).
2. **Set the maximum focus limit.** Move the camera closer until the rear-most part of the specimen is in focus. Repeat the same procedure and assign the Max value with a small margin.
3. Adjust Step [Z Axis]. This parameter defines the increment between positions within the focus range and determines the number of images per viewpoint. A minimum of approximately **20 images per viewpoint** is recommended. For example:

$$-20000 \text{ to } -12000 \rightarrow \text{range} = 8000 \rightarrow \text{step} = 400 \rightarrow \frac{8000}{400} = 20 \text{ images/per viewpoint}$$

This ensures sufficient overlap between focused regions during focus stacking. Larger step values may result in gaps in focus, leading to reconstruction artifacts. Once configured, the setup should resemble the configuration shown in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6. Example of an optimal configuration for a specimen. The specimen is visible in the central display [*Start Live Preview*], along with the normalized color curves [*Highlight Exposure*].

Post Processing

Once image acquisition has been configured, this section defines the complementary processes that can be executed **in parallel with the scan**, such as focus stacking and automatic mask generation.

Post Processing Parameters

The parameters in this section remain disabled until the corresponding processes are activated. The recommended workflow is as follows:

1. Enable *Stack Images*. When this option is activated, scAnt performs focus stacking during the scanning process. After each viewpoint acquisition is completed, the default stacking software automatically generates an **EDOF (Extended Depth of Focus)** image, which is stored in the *stacked* folder of the project directory.
 - **Important:** The default stacking method is functional but may not always produce optimal results. An alternative workflow using external stacking software is discussed later in this document.
2. Enable *Threshold Images* and adjust *Threshold (focus)*. This parameter defines how sharp an image must be to be included in the stacking process. Higher values apply stricter selection criteria, meaning only sharper images will contribute to the final stack. This parameter is highly sensitive to image noise, resolution, and specimen size. In most cases, it is recommended to **keep the default value or increase it slightly** (e.g., a value of 2).
3. Enable *Mask Images*. When activated, scAnt generates an alpha mask for each stacked (EDOF) image. Specimen contours are detected using a pre-trained random forest model, after which the background is removed through adaptive thresholding based on pixel brightness values. This process automatically

separates the specimen from the background, facilitating subsequent 3D reconstruction.

4. Define *Threshold (masking)* values. This step defines the minimum and maximum threshold values used for background removal during mask generation. To obtain these values, an external image editor such as GIMP is required (**Fig. 7**). The recommended procedure is: 1) Capture an image using *Capture Image*; 2) Open the image in GIMP; 3) Use the *Color Picker* tool to obtain RGB values from the background, preferably near the specimen; 4) Repeat this process multiple times to determine the minimum and maximum background values; and 5) Enter these values into the masking threshold parameters.

Once configured, scAnt should be able to correctly identify and remove the background without affecting the specimen.

Figure 7. Example workflow for obtaining RGB threshold values in GIMP. The *Color Picker* tool is displayed in the upper-right corner of the image, showing the RGB values.

Processing Output

In this section, the directory containing the RAW images generated during the scanning process must be specified (i.e., the *RAW* folder). scAnt uses this location to identify the acquired images and apply the post-processing operations configured in the previous steps.

Once this configuration is completed, the setup should resemble the example shown in **Figure 8**. At this stage, the scanning process can be started using *Start Scan*. Before doing so, remember to disable both *Highlight Exposure* and *Live Preview*.

Figure 8. Example of a post-processing configuration for a specimen of *Carabus ghiliani*.

3D Reconstruction (Metashape)

Once the scanning process in scAnt has been completed, the next step is to generate the 3D model from the acquired images. For this purpose, **Agisoft Metashape** is used, one of the most robust software solutions currently available for photogrammetric reconstruction. The main limitation of Metashape is that it is [commercial software](#).

Project Setup in Metashape

After launching the software, the first step is to create and save a new project (*File* → *Save*) in the desired directory. It is recommended to save the project within the same folder generated by scAnt, where the RAW images, stacked images, and masks are stored.

Once the project has been created, the stacked images must be imported:

1. Open the *Workspace* panel.
2. Select *Add > Add Photos...* (**Fig. 9**).
3. Navigate to the folder containing the stacked images generated by scAnt.
4. Select all images and confirm the import.

Figure 9. Metashape graphical interface showing the tabs used to import images.

If the import process was successful, approximately **180 TIFF images** should be available (or the corresponding number depending on the axis configuration used during acquisition).

Mask Import or Generation

Once the images appear inside the *Chunk* in the *Workspace* panel (upper-left section of the interface), masks can be incorporated to facilitate the reconstruction process. At this stage, there are two possible approaches:

- **Import Masks Generated by scAnt**

This option imports the masks automatically generated during the scanning process. Procedure:

1. Right-click any image in the *Photos* panel.
2. Select *Masks > Import Masks...* (**Fig. 10**).
3. Choose the folder containing the masks generated by scAnt.
4. The masks will be imported automatically.

- **Generate Masks Directly in Metashape**

Metashape also provides an AI-based mask generation tool. Procedure:

1. Right-click any image in the *Photos* panel.
2. Select *Masks > Generate Masks...* (**Fig. 10**)
3. Confirm the dialog window by clicking **OK**. Metashape will then automatically generate masks for all imported images.

Figure 10. Context menu displayed after right-clicking an image, showing the available *Mask* options.

Once the process has started, Metashape will generate the masks sequentially (**Fig. 11**). After a short processing period, masks for all images should be available.

Figure 11. Example of the AI-based mask generation process in Metashape.

Batch Process (Optional but Highly Recommended)

Once the masks have been imported or generated, the 3D reconstruction workflow can begin. This process may be performed step by step manually or automated using the *Batch Process* tool. To access this feature: *Workflow > Batch Process*. Within this panel, different reconstruction stages can be added using the *Add* button, their execution order can be defined, and the parameters for each process can be configured. Using *Batch Process* allows all reconstruction stages to run automatically in sequence, eliminating the need to manually launch each step after the previous one finishes (**Fig. 12**).

The recommended workflow is shown in **Figure 12**. However, each reconstruction stage and its recommended configuration will be explained individually in the following sections. While these settings may not be optimal for every type of organism, they generally produce high-quality 3D reconstructions.

Important: From this point onward, all screenshots and examples correspond to the parameter windows available through the *Batch Process* interface. Although the interface may differ slightly when processes are executed individually, the parameters and recommended settings remain the same.

Figure 12. Recommended reconstruction workflow using the *Batch Process* tool.

Recommended 3D Reconstruction Workflow

1. Image Alignment and Sparse Point Cloud Generation

Go to: *Workflow > Align Photos* (or add the process directly through *Batch Process*). The recommended settings are shown in **Figure 13**, although some parameters may be adjusted depending on the available computational resources and reconstruction quality requirements:

- **Accuracy:** This parameter can be reduced to **Medium** to decrease processing time, although alignment quality may also decrease. Whenever possible, it is recommended to keep this parameter at the highest available setting.
- **Reset Current Alignment:** If the alignment partially fails, repeat the process with *Reset current alignment = Yes* enabled. This removes the previous alignment before recalculating it.

Once the process is complete, it is important to verify the proportion of aligned images (*aligned images/total images*) and the total number of generated tie points. This information can be found in the *Workspace* panel after expanding *Chunk 1* (**Figure 12**).

Important: Non-aligned images usually appear in incorrect positions, generating artifacts such as isolated point clouds or planes located away from the main reconstruction cluster. In the *Photos* panel:

- Properly aligned images display a gray check mark
- Selected aligned images are highlighted in red in the 3D view.

If a high proportion of images fail to align, the following steps are recommended:

1. Review the generated masks.

2. Repeat the alignment using different parameters.
3. Check the quality of the stacked images.

Figure 13. Parameter window for the *Align Photos* process showing the recommended configuration.

2. Dense Point Cloud Construction.

To generate the dense point cloud, go to: *Workflow > Build Point Cloud* (or add the process directly through *Batch Process*). The recommended settings are shown in **Figure 14**. Among the available parameters, *Quality* can be reduced to **Medium** or **Low** if computational resources are limited. However, for optimal reconstruction quality, it is strongly recommended to keep this parameter set to **Ultra High** whenever possible.

Figure 14. Parameter window for the *Build Point Cloud* process showing the recommended configuration.

Once this process is completed, a preliminary version of the final model can already be visualized.

3. **Mesh Construction (Optional).** At this stage, the current *Chunk* can optionally be duplicated within the *Workspace* panel (only possible if the reconstruction is being performed step by step rather than through *Batch Process*). Renaming the duplicated *Chunk* beforehand is recommended to preserve a backup of the previous reconstruction stage in case it is necessary to revert changes later. To generate a mesh from the dense point cloud: *Workflow > Build mesh*. Within the configuration window:

- a. Select *Depth Maps* as the source data
- b. Enable *Vertex Colors*

In most cases, no additional parameter modifications are required. However, the interpolation mode may not always produce optimal results. In some cases, setting interpolation to *Disabled* can improve the reconstruction quality.

4. **3D Model Construction.** Once the dense point cloud has been generated (the mesh is optional but often recommended), the following option becomes available: *Workflow > Build Model*. This step can also be configured beforehand within the *Batch Process* workflow. The recommended settings are shown in **Figure 15** and generally provide high-quality reconstructions for most specimens. Once the process is complete, the reconstructed model can be visualized in different display modes:

- a. *Model - Shaded*: realistic shaded visualization.
- b. *Model - Solid*: solid-color representation.
- c. *Model - Wireframe*: polygonal mesh structure.
- d. *Model - Confidence*: confidence values across the model surface.

Figure 15. Parameter window for the *Build Model* process showing the recommended configuration.

5. **Texture Generation.** After model construction, the generated surface usually contains only a basic texture representation. To improve realism, a texture can be generated from the original images. To do this: *Workflow > Build Texture* (or add the process within *Batch Process*). In most cases, the default settings are sufficient (**Fig. 16**). However, if desired, the texture output can be divided into multiple texture files by adjusting:
 - a. *Count* → number of texture images.
 - b. *Texture Size* → resolution of each texture image.

Figure 16. Parameter window for the *Build Texture* process showing the recommended configuration.

6. **Exporting the Final Model.** After completing all previous steps, the reconstruction workflow is finished, and the resulting model should resemble the example shown in **Figure 17**.

Figure 17. Example of a successful 3D reconstruction.

To export the model for use in most 3D software:

File > Export > Export Model

Recommended format: COLLADA (.dae)

Recommended export settings:

- ✓ *Vertex colors.*
- ✓ *Export texture.*
- Filetype = TIFF.

scAnt vs. Helicon Focus: Image Stacking Limitations

As mentioned throughout this document, scAnt automatically performs focus stacking for each viewpoint using its built-in stacking software. While functional, the resulting stacked images are often noticeably inferior to those generated using dedicated focus-stacking software such as **Helicon Focus**. **Figure 18** compares the same viewpoint processed using both methods: Helicon Focus (left) and the default scAnt stacking workflow (right).

Figure 18. Comparison between stacked images generated using Helicon Focus (left) and scAnt (right) from the same image set.

These differences in stacking quality directly affect the final 3D reconstruction. As shown in **Figure 19**, the model reconstructed using the stacked images generated by scAnt (left) presents lower overall quality compared to the reconstruction obtained using images stacked in Helicon Focus (right).

Figure 19. Comparison between 3D reconstructions generated using stacked images from scAnt (left) and Helicon Focus (right).

This naturally raises the question: why not always use Helicon Focus for image stacking? The main limitation is the substantial increase in workflow duration. Using Helicon Focus requires a largely manual workflow:

1. Use scAnt exclusively for RAW image acquisition.
2. Open Helicon Focus and manually select the image set corresponding to each viewpoint (**Fig. 20**).
3. Render the stacked image within Helicon Focus.
4. Save the resulting image in a separate directory.
5. Repeat the process for all viewpoints (typically ≈ 180).

Even under optimized conditions (e.g., 21 images per viewpoint and 180 viewpoints), this process may require at least one additional hour of work. However, despite the increased processing time, the final image quality and reconstruction quality is significantly improved.

Figure 20. Example workflow for focus stacking in Helicon Focus. RAW images generated by scAnt are organized in the left panel, while the selected image set is processed and rendered within Helicon Focus on the right panel.

Useful References and Resources

scAnt

- Official repository containing source code, documentation, and downloadable files: [scAnt GitHub Repository](#)
- Webinar introducing the scAnt workflow and capabilities: [scAnt Webinar \(YouTube\)](#)
- Video presentation of the scAnt system and scanning workflow: [scAnt: Open-Source Macro 3D Scanner \(YouTube\)](#)
- Plum, F., & Labonte, D. (2021). *scAnt*—an open-source platform for the creation of 3D models of arthropods (and other small objects). *PeerJ*, 9:e11155. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.11155>

Agisoft Metashape

- Basic Metashape Tutorial (Video): [Photogrammetry demo in Agisoft Metashape](#)
- Official support forum for troubleshooting and workflow discussions related to Metashape: [Agisoft Metashape Forum](#)